

ERROR ANALYSIS OF PASSIVE IN THE WRITINGS OF ALBANIAN LEARNERS OF ENGLISH

Linguistics

Keywords: Be, modal, transitive, non-transitive, by, passive voice, contrastive analysis, erroranalysis, data analyzing.

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Abstract

The aim of this thesis is the analysis of errors commonly made in the 9-th grade students in urban and rural Albanian schools in the academic year 2018-2019 in using the passive voice. A quantitative approach is applied in conducting the research. The samples of the research are 24 students in both schools, 12 students in each school. The descriptive analysis method is going to be used in this research to find the errors of the students and to analyze the data. "The major focus of this study is the Contrastive Analysis between the English passive forms through their Albanian correspondents; contribute to the theoretical linguistics, to the general theory of contrastive linguistics, to the development of contrastive studies in Albanian, to the development of Albanian prescriptive grammars."¹ They are the theories of English grammar, Error analysis, and Language Teaching and Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis. Theory of English grammar was used to know and understand the structure of English passive voice. While, the theory of error analysis was used to analyze the student's errors based on the Linguistic Category Taxonomy particularly for the English passive voice, and Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis was used to find out the similarity and the difference between English and Albanian passive voice. My assumption is that the difficulties the Albanian learners of English face are due to the following: 1. English and Albanian being typologically two different languages, bilingual ones: a. English as a typical analytical language.² b. The paradigm of the verb in the Albanian language is very wealthy in word-form. It includes 251 analytic and synthetic forms, from them, 49 are synthetic forms. These synthetic forms are built mostly using two grammatical tools: "ndajshitesat eptimore" which play the main role, in the verb eptim, and morphological changing, to which play not only the matter role in the grammatical forms building.³ 2. The English language in comparison with the Albanian and other languages has a lot of similarities and differences in passives. In the following study, research is to point out and to find differences and similarities between English and Albanian passives. Both of those languages have to be understood by the learners prior to learning the target language. *First*, besides, the Albanian learners in learning the English language are frequently influenced by Albanian structure and to transfer the forms and meanings from Albanian native language to the English language. Second, the results of data analysis clearly show that most passives are marked with "jam" dhe "folje ne te tashme" dhe "pjesore e shkuar e disa foljeve te shqipes ne prapashtesa -re (ne bere), -ar (ne punuar)", which are also translated into passive in English ("be" plus 'past participle') plus "by-agent". Some passives, namely translated into passives in English and some others are translated into actives. Third, in translating Albanian passives into English shifts inevitably take place on a grammatical level, on the aspect of tense. Part of the study is transitive, non-transitive, infinitives, its structure and the omission of it, participles and its comprehensions, gerunds, the structure and the use of them that change a lot from both languages, including the forms of -ing in comparing to English, the forms of "pa larë, me të larë dhe një të larë", which do not have forms, changing the forms of tenses, the use of "by- phrase", passive clauses, incorrectness of "be" and its omission, the correct use of conditionals, the misspelling of modals, wrong using of the order of passives, misformation of conditionals, the future "going to", modals, passive infinitives all in passives.

I. Introduction

In general terms, this study is concerned with different aspects of morphosyntax seen from the point of view of the two languages; English and Albanian. Grammar is traditionally divided into two different but interrelated areas of study: *morphology and syntax*.

¹ Gurra, H. The Similarities and Differences between English and Albanian Progressive Tenses in Terms of Manner Form Usage Aspect and Modality. Vol. 4, No.4, June 2014 <http://www.mcser.org/journal/index.php/jesr/article>

² Memushaj, R. Morfonologji e Eptimit te Gjuhës se Sotme Shqipe. Ndërrimet Morfonologjike ne Eptimin Foljor, 1989, f. 149, kreu IV, 107.

³ Ibid 2

However, now, these two areas are often combined into one unity called morphosyntax. The word *morphosyntactic* is the adjective of *morphosyntax*. Morphosyntax is derived from *morphology* which is the study of word formation and *syntax* which is the study of how words are combined into a larger unit such as phrase and sentence. Morphosyntax is a combination of morphology and syntax. They are combined because they have a very close relationship.”⁴ According to Crystal⁵ *morphosyntax* is a term in linguistics used to refer to grammatical categories or properties for whose definition criteria of morphology and syntax both apply, as in describing the characteristics of words.

Albanian language, just like English, is part of Indo-European language family, but it has a special place in it. The Indo-European character of the language was first recognized in Vienna 1854 by the German linguist Franz Bopp in his “Über das Albanesische in seinen verwandtschaftlichen Beziehungen”. Albanian (Shqip [ʃcip], or gjuha shqipe [ˈjuha ˈʃcipɛ]) is a language of the Indo-European family, in which it occupies an independent branch. It is an official language in Albania and Kosovo and has official minority status in Italy, Romania, Montenegro, Serbia, Macedonia and others. The language has official status in Ulcinj, southern Montenegro. Albanian is also spoken by large Albanian communities elsewhere in Europe, the Americas, and Australia. (Franz Bopp).⁶ According to the Albanian Linguist E. Çabej.⁷ Albanian language is a sister, not a descendant of the Indo-European family. Although both languages belong to the Indo-European family, in addition to common features in the phonetic, semantic and grammatical system, they naturally have differences from one another.⁸ In this paper, I will try to point out some of main similarities and differences of these two languages in the syntactic level, which should be considered not only during the translation from one of these languages to the other but also in a better acquisition of either Albanian or English. Based on the ideas of the above background, it is obvious that learning target language, which in this case, is English, will tend to lead to some problems for the learners particularly in the use of the English passive voice. The present study attempted to investigate the problems formulated as below:

- What are the kinds of errors commonly of the 9th grade of urban and rural Albanian students in the academic year 2018-2018 in the use of passive voice?
- What are the causes of errors in using passive sentences in writing made of the 9th grade of urban and rural Albanian students in the academic year 2018-2019?
- What is the similarity and difference between English and Albanian passive voice?
- What are the problems faced by the students of the 9th grade in Albanian English schools in using English passive voice?

⁴ Crystal Davis. 1980. A First Dictionary of linguistics and Phonetics. 1980:234. English Morphosyntactic Structure, 2010. <http://my-uad-courses.blogspot.com/2010/09/english-morphosyntactic-structure.html>

⁵ Ibid 4

⁶ Aida Kurani Syntactic Similarities and Differences between Albanian and English... 1854 by the German linguist Franz Bopp in his Über das ... According to the Albanian Linguist E. Çabej: Albanian language is a sister, not a descendant of the Indo-European family. Publisher: European Scientific Institute, ESI. (E. Çabej, Studime Etimologjike në fushë të Shqipërisë I, 1982, pp. 35-48.)

⁷ <http://eujournal.org/index.php/esj/article/viewFile/4690/4482>

⁸ Ibid 6

⁸ Ibid 6

II. Literature Review

2.1 The concept of English passive voice

Eckersley⁹ said that, if the person or thing denoted by the subject of a sentence is the receiver or sufferer of the action, then that form of the verb is the passive voice, e.g. “The ball was kicked by the boy”.

“According to Quirk¹⁰ in all passive clause types, the agent ‘by-phrase’, which incorporates a noun phrase equivalent to the subject of the corresponding active clause, has the structural status of an optional adverbial. Even when the agent ‘by-phrase’ is absent, however, there is an implication of its presence at the level of meaning. In this sense, the agent ‘by-phrase’ acts as complementation of the passive verb.”

2.2 The concept of error analysis

Most of the researchers pay attention to the analysis of grammatical errors in foreign language acquisition. Corder is among the first researchers who stress the importance of finding and correcting errors in students' written assignments or in communication. According to him, the errors are important for students. Errors are necessary during language acquisition. Error Analysis can be a very useful device in foreign language teaching. According to Norrish, Richards(ed),¹¹ errors' analysis offers us a clear view of students' language development and gives us clear instructions to the learning process, grammatically correct, but not interpretable in the context of communication, while overtones are not statements formulated based on the grammatical rules.

Ellis¹² connects kinds of errors to the level of students and types of activities. He says that beginners make more errors, because of the influence of mother tongue interference, while the most advanced students, due to lack of language skills or incorrect application of the rules. In his later studies, in addition to these sources of errors students, Richards adds other types of errors sources as the influence of native language, errors in the use of linguistic structures. In their research studies Kutz, Groden, Zamel¹³, claim that the factors that influence students' errors are the translation of sentences from their native language to the foreign one, the generalization of grammatical rules of the language and above all their uncertainty to express what they aim.) Since the errors of performance are known to be systematic, the teachers of English should be aware of the system of errors. Errors provide feedback; they tell the teachers something about the effectiveness of his teaching materials and his teaching techniques and show him/her what parts of

⁹ Difficulties in Learning and Producing Passive Voice, International conference on Linguistic, Literature and Culture, 175, p.10. Resource Studies, Eckersley, H. A Comprehensive of English Grammar, 1960: 219-224 Quirk et.al. A Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language, 1985:58 <https://dspace.aab-edu.net>

¹⁰ Ibid 9

¹¹ Norrish, J. *Language Learning and their Errors*, 1987:8, Richards(ed), *Error Analysis*, 1973:97

¹² Ellis, R. *Case study on the Analysis of Albanian Students' English Copular*, 1993:879-903. Resource Studies, *Difficulties in Learning and Producing Passive Voice*). International Journal of Human Resource Studies, 2162-3058 2014, pp.174-175, Vol.5, No.1. www.macrothink.org/journal/index.php/ijhrs/article/download/7333/6055

¹³ Kutz, Groden and Zamel, *The discovery of competence: Teaching and Learning with Diverse Student Writers*. College English, Vol. 55.8, 1993, pp. 879-903

the syllabus he/she has been following or taught and need further attention. Mistakes are made by a group of Albanian students of English during their Classroom Oral Interactions. Oral interaction in the classroom is very important because sometimes it is the only opportunity for students to use a foreign language. When a student starts learning a foreign language, he/she already possesses some rules in his/her unconscious. However, in a foreign language, this is an artificial process, requiring an abstraction from our native language or culture. Moreover, the knowledge of other languages may lead students to make wrong inferences. Also, one must not forget that written language implies an organization different from that of spoken language. In writing, logic and coherence are essential for communication, whereas, in speaking, this may compensate for the eventual gaps with paralanguage, which renders communication much more efficient. As teachers, we very often forget that students' only chance to communicate in a foreign language is inside the classroom. Outside it, they tend to use the foreign language to listen to songs, to play computer games, and sometimes in chat-rooms''¹⁴ In language acquisition, according to the Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis formulated by Lado¹⁵, difficulties in acquiring a new (second) language are derived from the differences between the new language and the native (first) language of a language user.

2.3 Passive learning difficulties

According to the literature on the structure of Albanian, Demiraj and Kallulli¹⁶ Albanian is described as a free word order language. However, the unmarked order of constituents in a transitive construction is considered to be SVO, as in the following example: The letter *was written* by the boy.

On the communicative or pragmatic level, the passive has made it unfashionable it sounds more learned, more complex, "sophisticated and academic". The "conventional" *subject-verb-object* S-V-O sentence structure, where the object is identified as the patient, account for a large majority of world languages. This compels the conclusion that the S-V-O word order, in which the initial place in the sentence is conventionally occupied by the agent, is more commonly used, more natural, direct, clear and concise, so its communicative function is more emphasized, more openly directed toward the listener or the reader, or the receiver of communication. On the surface level, the passive is simply wordier, because, in order to form it, we have to employ the auxiliary verb *to be*. Grammatically, it requires skill and adept knowledge of several distinct grammatical participles.

Renditja e fjaleve ne sintagme dhe ne fjali si mjet per shprehjen e kuptimeve gramatikore, ku me shume e ku me pak, vepron ne cdo gjuhe. Por ne disa prej tyre, ku eptimi mungon, rendi i fjaleve paraqitet si mjeti themelor per shprehjen e funksioneve te fjaleve ne fjali. psh. ne anglishte, kryefjala qendron gjithnje para kallzuesit, kurse kundrinori prapa tij. Po te permbyset ky rend, atehere kryefjala behet kundrinor e kundrinori kryefjale, si psh.

The hunter killed the wolf.

'Gjahtari vrau ujkun.'

¹⁴ Arburim iseni (Online) Iseni. ... JEP@iiste.org. ISSN (Paper) ...January 2013 <https://www.researchgate.net/.../281906288>

¹⁵ Lado, R. *Linguistics Across Cultures: Applied Linguistics for Language Lecturers*, 1957

¹⁶ Shaban Demiraj, *Gjuha Shqipe dhe Historia e Saj*, 1988 and Kallulli, D. *Critics in Albanian*, 1995

The wolf killed the hunter.

‘Ujku vrau gjahtarin.’

Gjuhë si anglishtja, ku rendi i fjaleve merr vlere, si shprehes i marredhenieve gramatikore, quhen gjuhe me *rendte ngulitur*.¹⁷

Another compelling argument “against” the passive is derived from our students’ mother tongue, Albanian. Since all the observations made throughout this searching are based on experiences from the Albanian ESP classroom, it may be deserving of consideration to mention briefly the status of the passive voice in the students’ native language.

2.4 *The necessity of the passive for students*

After considering all the “negative” aspects of the passive voice and almost arriving at the conclusion that it has become old, why is it still necessary for students to acquire it and use it competently?

First of all, even though the use of the passive seems to be resisted from many sides, it is beyond question that it has an innate capability to turn an utterance into a more impersonal, detached and thus more formal statement by removing the agent (subject) of the action from the sentence, which is a requirement in technical, scientific and academic writing.

Furthermore, the syntactic features of the passive are rather simple and straightforward in that the rules are elementary and unambiguous: it is just a different way of showing who is doing the action in a sentence and who is receiving it. The object (patient) of the active sentence becomes the subject (agent) of the passive one, and then the verb assumes the passive shape (auxiliary *to be* and past participle of the main verb), followed by an optional remark on the object (or the subject of the passive sentence), and indicated prepositionally (*by*).

Teaching English passive is included in English instruction in most education levels. During my teaching experiences, I have found that a large number of Albanian learners, from the grade of 3 until the high school (10-12 level) cannot use the English passive correctly.

English and Albanian grammar were presented in order to explain the structure of the passive voice. Students show a lot of difficulties, as they are unfamiliar in using it properly.

2.5 *The causes of errors*

Errors may be caused by several factors. According to Norrish,¹⁸ the causes of errors can be classified into three types namely carelessness, first language interference, and translation

2.5.1. *Carelessness*

Carelessness is related to lack of motivation. If students are lack of motivation in learning or writing assignments, it will be easier for them to make errors. Norrish¹⁹ mentions, “It is not

¹⁷ Rami Memushaj, *Hyrje ne Gjuhesi*, 2004, f. 220-221, 4.2.5.2, Rendi i fjalëve.

¹⁸ Norrish, J. *Language Learners and their Errors*, 1983:47/21/22/26. Ratmo, S.Pd., M.MPd, 2017, *Error Analysis on the Use of Passive Voice in Students’ Thesis Proposal*.

openjournal.unpam.ac.id/index.php/Paradigma/article/download/411/337

¹⁹ Ibid 21

always the students' fault if he loses interest; perhaps the materials and/or the style of presentation do not suit him." It means that students could be bored by the materials themselves because of the contents or the way they are written or presented.

2.5.2 First language interference

First language interference may lead to errors in students' language learning. Norrish²⁰ states, "It was commonly believed until fairly recently that learning a language (a mother tongue or a foreign language) was a matter of habit formation." It means that first language interference occurs when old habits (in mother tongue) interfere with new habits in the target language.

The learner's utterances were thought to be gradually 'shaped' towards those of the language he was learning. With the mother tongue, for example, sounds were uttered by the young child which was resembled by approval of his parents. It was this rewarding, either by increased attention from his parents or the child's wants being satisfied, which led in turn to the repetition of the utterance and subsequently found the formation of linguistic habit.

2.5.3 Translation

The most common errors occur when learners try to translate his first language (mother tongue) sentences into the target language. As Norrish²¹ states that translating word by word especially of idiomatic expression can produce classic howlers.

2.6 Verb as a grammatical category

Huddleston (2002:91)²² provides a brief definition of a verb saying that "a verb denotes an action or a state of being". In addition, Eckersley²³ emphasizes the importance of the verb claiming that is present in a sentence in the majority of cases and that its role is essential.

A 'verb', from the Latin *verbum* meaning 'word,' is a word (part of speech) that in syntax conveys an action (bring, read, walk, run, learn), an occurrence (happen, become), or the particle *to*, is the infinitive. In many languages, verbs are inflected (modified in form) to encode *tense, aspect, mood, and voice*. A verb may also agree with the person, gender, and/or a number of some of its arguments, such as its subject, or object. Verbs have tenses: *present*, to indicate that an action is being carried out; *past*, to indicate that an action has been done; *future*, to indicate that an action will be done.²⁴

Ne gjuhen shqipe sipas Kostallarit²⁵ folja ka nje sistem te pasur trajtash gramatikore, me anen e te cilave shprehen kuptime te tilla si kuptimi i diatezes, i mënyrës, i kohës dhe i vetes. According to the British linguists Huddleston and Pullum²⁶ the verb functions as an ultimate

²⁰ Ibid 21

²¹ Ibid 21

²² Huddleston R. and Pullum K. G. *The Cambridge Grammar of the English Language*, Cambridge, 2002:91

²³ Eckersley, H. A *Comprehensive English Grammar*, 1983:143

²⁴ View Verb. pdf from accounting acc4997 at INTI International College Subang. <https://www.coursehero.com> > ... > accounting > accounting acc4997

²⁵ Androkli Kostallari, *Gjuha Letrare Shqipe per te gjithë*, 1976, f. 100, V, Folja

²⁶ Huddleston and Pullum, *A Student's Introduction to English Grammar*, Cambridge University 2005:50

head of a clause and has an essential role as it “determines what other kinds of elements are required or permitted” Bieber, Conrad, and Leech²⁷ divide verbs according to their ability to function as follows:

- Lexical verbs (e.g. *run, eat, think*) functioning only as main verbs.
- Primary verbs (*do, be, have*) functioning as both auxiliary verbs and main verbs.
- Modal verbs (*can, could, shall, should, will, would, may, might, must*) functioning only as auxiliary verbs.

However, the issue of verb classification is much more complex. Besides the three major verb categories (lexical verbs, primary verbs, and modal verbs) derived from a function of a verb in a verb phrase, there are many other aspects whose application gives rise to other verb classes.

Greenbaum²⁸ numbers seven categories as applied to verbs that are: “mood (*indicative, imperative, subjunctive*), modality (*modal auxiliaries*), tense (*present, past*), aspect (*perfect, progressive*), number (*singular, plural*), person (*first, second, third*), and voice (*active, passive*)”. Thus, verbs as part of speech, except showing an action or a state, they can be classified according to their function. This leads to a classification of verbs in a multitude of grammatical categories.

2.7 Forms of the verb

Following, there are three different types of verbs defined by Eckersley²⁹ through which sentence structure and particularly passive sentences are constructed.

Finite and Non-Finite Verbs. Format e shtjelluara dhe te pashtjelluara.

Regular and Irregular Verbs. Foljet e rregullta e te parregullta.

Transitive and Intransitive Verbs. Foljet kalimtare dhe jokalimtare

Thus, *finite verbs* through which a particular sentence is constructed show *tense, person and number*. *Non-finite* on the other hand do not show *tense, person, or number*. *Regular verbs* form their different tenses according to an established pattern. *Irregular verbs* do not follow the normal rules. A *transitive verb*, on the other hand, is one that is used with an object that refers to the person or thing that is affected by the action of the verb. *Intransitive verbs* are the contrary of the transitive they do not take an object.

In many languages, finite verbs are the locus of grammatical information of *gender, person, number, tense, aspect, mood, or voice*. In elementary level, finite verb is the verb in a sentence which determines the tense. *Finite verbs* are distinguished from *non-finite verbs*, such as *infinitives, participles*, etc, which generally mark these grammatical categories to a lesser degree or not at all, and which appear below the finite verb in the hierarchy of syntactic structure. They change through voice, they change in the time of speaking, the tense, they have a gender, a person,

²⁷ Bieber, Conrad and Leech *Student Grammar of Spoken and Written English*, 2002:15

²⁸ Greenbaum, S. *English Grammar*, 1996:79

²⁹ Eckersley, H. *A Comprehensive English Grammar*, 1960:143

a number. They have all the grammatical features that distinguish the verb as a verb. A *transitive verb* is followed by a *noun* or *noun phrase*.

My friend *read* the newspaper. The teenager *earned* a speeding ticket.

Quhen *kalimtare* ato folje, te cilat emertojne veprime, qe nuk mbeten tek ai qe e kryen, por shkojne e bien mbi nje person a send tjetër, qe ne fjali shprehet me ane te nje emri, peremri a cdo fjale tjetër te emerzuar ne rasen kallzore pa parafjale. Folje kalimtare pra quhen ato qe marrin kundrina te drejta. Te tilla jane foljet *dua*, *hap*, *kerkoj*, *marr*, *mbyll*, *nderoj*, *pershendet*, *qep*, etj. psh.

Plaku nuk *donte te kujtonte* asgje, por kujtimet i vinin verdalle si shtellunga tymi dhe ai nuk i *debonte* dot nga mendja...³⁰

Folja kalimtare i ka te dyja format si *veprore* dhe *pesore*. Ne diatezen veprore, kundrinori tregon objektin mbi te cilin bie veprimi. Ne gjuhen shqipe ka disa folje qe ne diatezen mesore, perdoren me nje kuptim te njejte ose te afert me formen pergjegjese te diatezes veprore, kur kjo ka veshtrim jo kalimtar, p.sh:

Po afronte koha e draperit te pare dhe shtegtimet te bagetive.(veprore)

Ndjente se po e linte fuqia, *sepo i afrohej* vdekja dhe nuk donte te jepej. (pesore)³¹

“Some of the transitive verbs in the Albanian language are: “*dua*”, “*hap*”, “*kërkoj*”, “*marr*”, “*mbyll*”, “*nderoj*”, “*përshëndet*” etc. Meanwhile intransitive verbs in Albanian are those verbs which denote an action which remains at its doer. Some of those intransitive verbs are: “*fle*”, “*rri*”, “*dal*”, “*eci*”, “*shkoj*”, etc.³²

Differently from other grammatical categories of verb (person, number, tense, mood) diathesis does not include all types of verbs. This way verbs that do not express some action but express state do not take diathesis, such verbs are: *jam* “to be”, *kam* “to have”, *di* “to know”, *rri* “to stay”, etc. Another group of verbs that cannot take objects are: *shkoj* “to leave”, *eci* “to walk”, *vrapoj* “to run”, *udhëtoj* “to travel”, etc. this group includes also verbs like *vdes* “to die”, *bie* “to fall”. This way depending on whether a verb takes a direct object or indirect object, verbs are divided into transitive and non-transitive.³³

Kostallari shpreh se *folje kalimtare* jane ato qe mund te marrin nje kundrine te drejte, e cila shprehet zakonisht me nje emer a peremer ne rasen kallzore pa parafjale, psh.: *hap* dritaren (open the window), *shkruaj* një letër ‘write a letter’, *tejkaloj* planin “surpass the plan”, etc.³⁴ Nga ana tjetër, *non-transitive verbs* ose *jokalimtare* quhen ato folje, te cilat emertojne veprime qe mbeten

³⁰ Agalliu, et al., Gramatika e Gjuhës Shqipe 1, *Morfologjia*, 2002, f. 265, Kreu VII, 7.2.3

³¹ Agalliu, et al., Gramatika e Gjuhës Shqipe 1, *Morfologjia*, 2002, f. 265, Kreu VII, 7.2.3 <https://www.scribd.com/doc/229348346/filer>

³² Sami Ibraimi and Arburim Iseni, *Modern English Grammar*, 2008, f. 58.

³³ Koleç Topalli, *Bazat e Gramatikës Historike të Gjuhës Shqipe*, 2011, f. 206-207.

³⁴ Andrea Kostallari, *Gjuha Letrare Shqipe per te Gjithe*, 1976, f. 100, Kreu V, Folja.

tek ai qe i kryen. Ato mund te tregojne *gjendje, levizje*, etj. Te tilla jane *fle, dremit, rri, dal, eci, hyj, shkoj, vrapoj, rroj*, etj. Keta folje nuk mund te marrin kundrinor te drejte, psh.

Në qepalla u *rendonte* gjumi e megjithatë nuk *flinin...*³⁵

In Albanian language, according to the possibility of changing or not changing, verbs are divided also into finite and non-finite verb forms. The finite verb form is called *forma e shtjelluar e foljes*, meanwhile the non-finite is called *forma e pashtjelluar e foljes*. The finite verb form in Albanian is changed in different moods, such as “deftore”:, (indicative), “habitore”, “kushtore”(conditional), “lidhore”(subjunctive), “deshirore” (optative), and “urdherore” (imperative), e.g.

Po shkoj ne shkolle. (indicative)

Po shkruaj nje leter. (indicative)

Do te laja njehere ne jave. (conditional)

E hapsha nje dere qe s’mbyllet kurre. (optative)

Cilesimi i nje foljeje si kalimtare ose jokalimtare varet ne shume raste nga kuptimi leksikor qe ka ajo ne fjaline ku eshte perdorur, psh.

Kalimtare Transitive

E fjeta mendjen

“Put my mind to sleep” *Fjeta shumë* “Slept too much” *Humba çelësin* “Lost the key” *Humba në gjumë* “Dropped in sleep” *Kaloj klasën* “Pass the grade” *Kaloj rrugës* “Pass the road” *Thërras shokët* “Call friends” *Thërras fort* “Outcry”.

Ndodhen tri lloje foljes ne anglisht dhe secila perdoret ne situata te ndryshme apo si zakonisht eshte thirrur kohe folje. Shembulli i foljeve qe perfshihen ne ato *jokalimtare*: ‘*die, go, arrive*’, nuk marrin kundrinor si rrjedhim nuk perdoret forma pesore.

I *go* to town (active)

Une *shkoj* ne qytet.

She *arrives* at seven o’clock

Ajo *arrin* ne oren 7.

Intransitive verbs such as *arrive, go, lie, sneeze* and *sit* cannot have a passive form simply because there is no object to rise to the status of the agent.

Some verbs which are normally considered intransitive, such as *walk* can be used transitively informally or in certain senses. For example: She *walked* the dogs → The dogs *were walked*

2.8 Ditransitive verbs

A ditransitive verb is an action verb with a direct object and an indirect object.

³⁵ Agalliu, et al., Gramatika e Gjuhës Shqipe 1, *Morfologjia*, 2002, f. 266, Kreu VII, 2

His dad promised *him a birthday party*.

Ditransitive verbs can normally have two passive versions, one in which the direct object becomes the subject: She bought it for me. (She ordered it for me.) (*prepositional dative*)

She bought me it. (She ordered it for me.) (*DOC*) She bought it me. (She ordered it for me.) (*theme-goal ditransitive*) Who did she give it (who)? (*prepositional dative*)

(Who) did she give it? (*DOC/theme-goal ditransitive*) are derived from a prepositional dative construction with a null/deleted to preposition³⁶ Ditransitive verbs (sometimes called Vg verbs after the verb *give*) precede either two noun phrases or a noun phrase and then a prepositional phrase often led by *to* or *for*. For example:

“The players *gave* their teammates high fives.”

“The players *gave* high fives to their teammates.”

When two noun phrases follow a transitive verb, the first is an indirect object, that which is receiving something, and the second is a direct object, that being acted upon. Indirect objects can be noun phrases or prepositional phrases.³⁷

2.9 Complex passive

It +verb+noun clause beginning with *that*:

It is said that the company might have been sold.

It is believed that most of the upper management will be replaced.

With an infinitive: noun phrase+passive verb+infinitive:

Our company is reported to have made a huge loss in his quarters.

Our company is a noun phrase, *is reported* is in the passive voice, *to have* an infinitive.

English can combine the passive with the full range of tense and aspect forms as well as modal verbs. For example:

She *will have been arrested*

The car *will be being serviced*

She *had been spoken to*

Some consider the complex forms combining progressive with perfect with passive with a modal to be clumsy but they are, nevertheless, possible in English.

Many languages, especially those with a more limited range of modal verbs, cannot do this

³⁶ Theme-Goal Ditransitives and Theme Passivisation ... p. 14. Queens College <http://qcpages.qc.cuny.edu/~whaddican/lingua-web.pdf>

³⁷ Sami Ibrahim and Arbrim Iseni, *Modern English Grammar*, 2008, f. 56

kind of thing. Unpacking what each auxiliary verb implies in such sentences is cognitive challenging and that leads to receptive error.

Inappropriate use of passive: A complex sentence is that combines, one independent clause with at least one dependent clause. Changing a complex sentence to active form:

Active sentence: They say (M.Cl.) that they have done the work. (S.Cl.)

Passive sentence: It is said that the work has been done by them.

When we buy his birthday cake, we have to make sure it's lemon.

(independent clause) (dependent clause)

Misusing passives in the complex sentence: *e.g.*

Mark was [^] hoped to become a football player.

Mark ushpresuate behej futbollist.

Dhe ne kete fjali mungon folja ‘*jam*’ (*be*) qe formon formen pesore. Por fjalia eshte ne trajtenpesore. Ne gjuhen shqipe behet me pjesezen u dhe pjesoren e shkuar te foljes qe mban veprimin, shpresua. Fjalia duhej te ishte:

Mark was being hoped to become a football player.

3.1 Double passives

Sometimes, the object of a verb is passive *to* complement. The verb *expect* is commonly used this way but there are others such as *to require*. For example:

We *require* you *to finish* the work (active sentence with *you* as the object of *requiring*)

We *require* the work *to be finished* (passive sentence 1 with *the work* as the patient)

You *are required to finish* the work (*by us*) (passive sentence 2 with *you* as the patient)

The work *is required to be finished* (*by you*) (passive sentence 3 – the double passive)

So, it is possible to make two passive sentences:

The police were given the information. Or the information was given to the police.

Other verbs that have two objects: *ask, offer, pay, show, teach, tell*.³⁸

Some people consider the double-passive construction to be clumsy, even wrong. It is certainly a form which learners are rarely going to need to produce but it crops up in written English more often than it should and takes a bit of unpacking to get at the meaning.

³⁸ Raymond Murphy, *English Grammar in Use*, 2012, p. 86, Unit 43

3.2 *Passive causatives*

Subject + have/get + object + past participle + (by-agent). We use the causative to say that we have arranged for someone to do something for us. Compare:

Mary *is having* her hair *cut*. (The hairdresser is cutting her hair).

Patric *is cutting* her hair.³⁹

Yesterday, my car broke down.

I had it fixed by a mechanic.

My hair is too long!

You should get (have) it cut!

My teeth hurt.

You should have them looked at by a doctor.

We use to *have something done* to say that we arrange for somebody else to do something for us:

Jill *repaired* the roof (she repaired it herself)

Jill *had the roof repaired*. (she arranged for somebody else to repair it).

You also can say ‘‘*get something done*’’ instead of ‘‘*have*’’:

I think you should *get the hair cut*.

But sometimes have a different meaning:

Jill *had* all their money *stolen* while she was on holiday. (This doesn't mean that she arranged for somebody to steal her money.)⁴⁰

Verbs in English ‘*make, let, have, get, help*’ are called *causative verbs* because they cause something else to happen. Here are some examples:

let/make/have/get, help+person/thing+verb (base form)

I don't *let* my children *watch* violent movies.

The teacher *made* all students *rewrite* their papers.

I'm going to *have* my hair *cut* tomorrow

He *helped* me *carry* the boxes

3.3 *Stative verbs*

Usually, verbs describe what something *does*. When we want to describe a condition (how it is), we use the special verb ‘‘*to be*’’. However, there are also a group of verbs, called *statives*(states) that describe the *state* of something. Here is an English joke, eg.

1. ‘‘My dog has no nose.’’

‘‘Oh, how does he smell?’’

‘‘He smells terrible.’’

³⁹Virginia Evans and Jenny Dooley, 2018, *Spark 4*, Teacher's book, p. 12, Grammar, 1b

⁴⁰Raymond Murphy, *English Grammar in Use*, 2012, p. 90, Unit 45.

The joke plays two different meanings of smell. One meaning is to sense an odor and the other meaning is to give off an odor. Since a dog smells with his nose, we assume that the verb is active. But the reply to the question takes the verb as *stative* and instead of telling is how the dog *doessomething*, it tells us something about the *state* of the dog (It needs a bath.)

2. I love this new shampoo. Don't you? I don't. It *smells*like flowers. Exactly.

The verb “*smell*” is a stative verbbecause it describes a state-something that just is. But here the verb ‘*smell*’ describes an action.

Some verbs do not have passive forms because they describe a state, not an action (*like, love, hate, believe, etc.*). *These are stative verbs*. Some stative verbs can have continuous forms but withdifferent meaning. *I think he's tired.* (belief)

I'm thinking of going home now. (considering).⁴¹But what's a passive stative? It is a special kind of the passive construction we're no longer expressing an action instead we're describing a state, a condition. The form is the same. It is seen that the form: “*be*” + *past participle*. There is no actionbeing expressed here instead the past participle *associated* describes the *song*, also the past participle *known* describes the author Ismail Kadare. The past participles *associated* and *known* function more like an adjective than a verb. Another thing we have to know is because we're not expressing an action.

The song *is associated* with Christmas.

Ismail Kadare *is known* as the best Albanian writer.

English uses the same verb (*be*) to form both a dynamic passive and a stative passive. For example:

Dynamic passive: During the game, the window *was broken*.

Stative passive: It was cold in the room because the window *was broken*.

In many languages, this confusion between state (arguably the adjectival use of the participle) and action is not possible because a different verb would be used in each case. For example, in German, the first sentence would be: *Das Fenster wurde gebrochen*, in which the verb *werden* signals the dynamic passive and in which the verb *sein* signals the stative passive.

Das Fenster war gebrochen.

Many other languages do something like that and the English use of “*be*” for both meanings is not immediately grasped. Learners who are looking for parallel constructions in English to those in their first languages may, therefore, be induced into errors such as: The window *became broken*.English can make a dynamic stative distinction with the verb ‘*get*’ as in, e.g.: The window *got*⁴² *broken* during the game and that will be intuitively acceptable to learners whose first languages routinely make the distinction.

⁴¹Virginia Evans and Jenny Dooley, 2018, *Spark 4*, p.12, Grammar, Express Publishing.

⁴²Sami Ibraimi and Arburim Iseni. *Modern English Grammar*, 2008, f. 374, Tringa Design. <https://www.linkedin.com/in/arburim-iseni-48141b34>.

The verb signals the passive in its first form (*was*) and the progressive in the second form (*being*).

Some verbs in English are almost always used in stative senses. These verbs are *understand, say*. Many stative passive verbs are followed *by prepositions* other than 'by'.

I am interested *in* English culture.

Many people aren't satisfied *with* the jobs they do.

State verbs nuk jane perdorur ne diatezen pesore edhe nese jane kalimtare (transitive). p.sh. *fit, have, belong, lack, resemble, suit etc.* Keto fjali nuk mund te kene diateze pesore.

They *have* a nice house (active).

Does this bag *belong* to you?

Sorry, these trousers *don't suit* me.⁴³

3.4 Verb voice

Since ancient times, diathesis has been analyzed in linguistic theories as a morphological category of the verb. Thus, while most of the languages distinguish diathesis in two types: active and passive, it could be noticed that other languages mention active, passive and middle verbs. Most theoretical studies recognize, in addition to the active voice, a single non-active voice, *passive*. The term *middle* is not used to denote voice; rather, it is usually restricted to a form of the verb denoting *disposition*, as in *the bread cuts easily*.

In descriptive and typological studies, on the other hand, a distinction can be found between two different non-active voices: the passive and the middle voice. Several typological studies discuss the middle voice⁴⁴ (Geniušien, *The Typology of Reflexives*, 1987, Kemmer *The Middle Voice*, 1993, Klaiman, *Grammatical Voice*, 1991, Siewierska *The Passive: A Comparative Linguistic Analysis*, 1984) and attempt to provide descriptions of its semantics. Though these descriptions have proven hard to sharpen and explicate in theoretical terms, it is nevertheless striking that the same traits repeat themselves in the descriptions of the middle voice from various languages of different language families. Topalli⁴⁵ claims that the traditional Albanian papers define diathesis or voice as a morphological category that expresses relations between the verb (the traditional predictor) and the subject. There has been made a division between active and non-active voice. Non-active voice verbs are further divided into passive, reflexive and middle voice. Voice: Active Non-active Passive Reflexive Middle. Verbs that belong to the reflexive voice category have their passive forms and denote an action that the subject performs and receives as well. In relation to the reflexive voice category, there is a sub-classification where the subject of the sentence represents the person acting on itself, and the verb is inherently reflexive, e.g. *krihem*

⁴³ Sami Ibraimi and Arburim Iseni. *Modern English Grammar*, 2008, f. 374, Tringa Design. <https://www.linkedin.com/in/arburim-iseni-48141b34>.

⁴⁴ Geniušien, E. *The Typology of Reflexives*, 1987, Kemmer, S. *The Middle Voice*, 1993, Klaiman, M.H. *Grammatical Voice*, 1991, Siewierska *The Passive: A Comparative Linguistic Analysis*, 1984

⁴⁵ Koleç Topalli, *Bazat e Gramatikës Historike të Gjuhës Shqipe*, 2011, f. 206-207

‘‘comb myself’’, *lahem* ‘‘wash myself’’, *vishem* ‘‘dress myself’’.⁴⁶

I would never mistake him for someone else, no matter that all *were dressed* similarly, with coveralls and boots’’

Kurrës’ mund ta ngatërrojaatë me ndonjëjtjetër, sadoqëtëgjithë *ishinveshurnjësoj*, me kominoshedhecizme).

Verbs belonging to the middle (medium) voice are in passive form and denote an action performed by the subject. The medium voice category comprises a group of verbs which denote movement such as *hidhem* ‘‘jump’’, *kthehem* ‘‘turn’’, *përpiqem* ‘‘try’’, *rrotullohem* ‘‘turn over’’.

When he received the news, he *tried to get up* and grab the weapons and gave orders to get his horse ready. Kur mori lajmin, *u përpoq të ngrihej* e të kapte armët dhe dha urdhër t’i pergatitnin kalin. Some verbs denoting physiological actions such as *gëzohem*, ‘‘rejoice’’ *hidhërohem*, ‘‘grieve’’ *mërzitem*, ‘‘get bored’’ *kollem*, ‘‘cough’’ example and some verbs that denote changes in physical, physiological, psychological state of the subject, such as *plakem* ‘‘get old’’, *rritem* ‘‘grow’’, *tkurrem* ‘‘shrink’’. He was not *bored* by hearing events from the life of a man poured into the bronze. Ai nuk *mërzitej* duke dëgjuar ngjarje nga jeta e njeriut të derdhur në bronx. *He shrunk, clamped* and stretched his hands toward his wounds to stop the blood. *Utkurr, u mbloodh* kruspull dhe zgjati duart drejt plagëve per të ndaluar gjakun. Kallulli⁴⁷ claims that the Albanian language possesses a class of lexically non-active verbs, which are verbs that do not have active forms. Typically, raising verbs in Albanian are lexically non-active.

Non active	Active
Kreno-hem	‘‘I am proud’’ → kreno-j
Zoto-hem	‘‘I swear’’ → zoto-j
Pendo-hem	‘‘I regret’’ → pendo-j
Dergj-em	‘‘I linger’’ → dergj
Drithero-hem	‘‘I shiver’’ → drithero-j

Topalli⁴⁸ claims that the category of diathesis has been notable since ancient times in the Indo-European languages where despite active voice, verbs had their special forms on passive voice, too. While active voice was quite common, the passive voice appeared later on. The latter differed from active voice because of the possession of different endings which were not the same for all languages of this family. In the Albanian language, the grammatical category of diathesis is formed through three different tools: *helping verbs*, *endings*, and *the clitic-u*. Each of the tools above mentioned conjugate according to the verb’s mood, number, person, and tense.

Verbs in present, imperfect, future and future perfect of indicative, subjunctive and conditional mood are conjugated with the following endings: *-em/hem*, *-esh/hesh*, *-et/het*, *-emi/hemi*, *-eni/heni*, *-en/hen*, *-esha/-hesha*, *-eshe/-heshe*, *-ej (-esh)/ -hej(-hesh)*, *-eshim/-heshit*, *-eshit/-heshit*, *-eshin/-heshin*. Some other verbs in present, imperfect, past, non-finite, and future

⁴⁶ Hyreme Gurra, The Similarities and Differences Between English and Albanian Progressive Tenses In Terms of Manner Form Usage Aspect and Modality, 2014: 162, Vol. 4 No.4 5.4. Journal of Educational and Social Research MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy

⁴⁷ Dalina Kallulli, Non-active Morphology in Albanian and Event (De) composition, f. 22 (1999: 444).

https://filologjiku.uni-gjkg.org/upload/.../73781-Anglisht_Fjolla%20Asllani.pdf

⁴⁸ Kolec Topalli, Bazat e Gramatikës Historike të Gjuhës Shqipe, 2011, f. 201.

perfecttake the clitic-*u* based on their corresponding moods. The helping verb –*jam* conjugates all verbs in past and future tenses. In the following page, there is a more detailed explanation for the three mentioned tools.

The Albanian language provides the same grammatical rules as the English language in the formation of the passive. The subject (person or thing) is the doer of an action in a sentence, that sentence is in an active voice. While the opposite the subject (person or thing) being a receiver of action, that sentence is considered to be in passive voice.

Agalliu et al.,⁴⁹ provides the following definition of diathesis/voice: Diateza është ajo kategori gramatikore, nepermjet se ciles shprehet lidhja midis veprimit te emertuar nga folja dhe kryefjales (te shprehur ose te nenkuptueshme) te fjalise. Lidhjet midis veprimit dhe kryefjales se fjalise morfologjikisht shprehen me dy pale forma, qe i kundervihen njera-tjetres dhe qe do te quhen *forma veprare* dhe *joveprare* te foljes (khs. *hap-hapem, hapa-u hapa, kam hapur-jam hapur*). Verbs additionally to showing time by their tense can show whether the subject is performing the action or having the action performed on it. This quality of a verb is known as *voice*.⁵⁰

The category of voice belongs to the linguistic features that can be found in the majority of languages and is defined variously in the literature. Huddleston⁵¹ defines voice as “a system where the contrasting forms differ in the way semantic roles are aligned with systematic functions”, this way according to their systematic properties sentences are proclaimed as *active* or *passive*.

According to Quirk et al.⁵² the difference between active and passive verb phrases that while participle of the main verb (e.g. *is kissed*), the active verb phrase is defined as one which does not contain this construction (e.g. *kisses*).

According to Eckersley⁵³ if the person or thing denoted by the subject of a sentence is the doer of the action, then that form of the verb is the active voice, e.g.

The man *kicked* the ball. (active voice)

If the person or thing denoted by the subject of a sentence is the receiver or sufferer of the action, then that form of the verb is the passive voice, e.g.

The ball *was kicked* by the man. (passive voice)

The passive voice is formed using the appropriate tense of the verb *to be* + the past participle of the verb.

Only the *transitive verbs* can be used in passive voice. The verbs of “incomplete predication” such as *seem, be, become*, etc., can never be used in passive; e.g.

He *became* King could never have a passive form such as A king ~~*was become*~~ by him.

Certain *intransitive verbs* can be made into *transitive* ones by the addition of a preposition. These verbs can be used in the passive voice, e.g.

His plan *was laughed* at by everyone who heard it.

That is a famous bed; it *was slept* in by Queen Elizabeth I.

⁴⁹ Agalliu et al., Gramatika e Gjuhës Shqipe 1, Morfologjia, Kategoria Gramatikore e Diatezes, 7.3.5, 2002, f. 270

⁵⁰ Forlin, 1982:209

⁵¹ Huddleston, R. The Cambridge Grammar of the English Language, 2002:1427

⁵² Quirk et al., A Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language, 1972:256

⁵³ Eckersley, H.A. *Comprehensive English Grammar*, 1960:219-224.

Though all transitive verbs can theoretically be made passive, there are cases where, in practice, the passive would not be used, for example:

He *had* a good breakfast before he went to work

Some verbs, such as *give, tell, show, lend, get, write, sell, buy, bring, make, fetch, promise, teach*, take two objects, one usually standing for a person, the other for a thing. The word for the person is an *indirect object* and is the first of the two objects; the word for the thing is a *direct object*, e.g.

He *sold* us (indirect) his house (direct). Here, *us* means, “to us”.

In Albanian verbs have an *active* and *passive voice*. It is formed in two ways. In the *present and imperfect tenses* simplified forms of auxiliary verb “*jam*” (I am) are added to the root of the word, eg.

“*rris*” I raise, “*rritem*”, I am raised”, “*rritesha*”, I was being raised.

If the root ends in a vowel, “*h*” is inserted before the auxiliary, eg.

“*Coj*”, I send; “*cohem*”, I am sent.

In the *past tense* and in *Imperative, Infinitive* and *Optative mood*, “*u*” the reflexive of the third person, is prefixed to active forms, eg.

“*Cova*”, I sent; “*u-cova*”, I was sent

“*Me prishe*”, to destroy,; “*me u- prishe*”, to be destroyed

One of the common features of Albanian language has an active and passive conjugation. In Albanian, the verbs which are used in more than one voice, as it is the case with the majority of the transitive verbs, have both the active and passive voice, whereas intransitive verbs mainly of the middle voice type *kollem*, have only one type of conjugation – the active conjugation, mainly passive.⁵⁴

3.5 Synthetic or analytical of the verb's paradigm during its conjugation

A synthetic verb can be defined as a complex semantic unit that can be analysed into a simple analytic construction consisting of a prime verb plus a morphologically related sentence constituent. A prime verb is a verb used within an analytic construction equivalent, completely in meaning and partially in form, to a synthetic verb (Liefrink, 1973: 17, 31).⁵⁵ The first group contains: *be, become, cause, do, give, have, make, put and take*. Whereas, the second group contains as many prime verbs as there are synthetic verbs whose analysis is made on collocational bases, like *takeoff* and *ride*.⁵⁶ Grammatical categories like tense, voice, or agreement can be expressed either by individual words or by affixes attached to some other word (or the stem of a word). If a word combines with affixes, the resulting construction is said to be *synthetic*; if not, it is said to be *analytic*. For example, in the past tense, the English verb combines with an affix expressing tense (cf. she *painted*, with suffix *-ed*). Forms like *painted* are called synthetic. In the future tense, by contrast, the verb does not combine with an affix; the future is instead expressed by a separate word (*will*, as in she *will paint*). Expressions like *will paint* are called *analytic*.⁵⁷ The

⁵⁴ *Akademia e Shkencave të Shqipërisë*, 1995, f. 276. Journal of Educational and Social Research MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy Vol. 4 No.6 September 2014.

⁵⁵ EA Mohsin, *Synthetic Verbs in English and French*, 2012 <https://www.iasj.net/iasj?func=fulltext&aId=68243>

⁵⁶ EA Mohsin, *Synthetic Verbs in English and French*, 2012 <https://www.iasj.net/iasj?func=fulltext&aId=68243>

⁵⁷ Balthasar Bickel and Johanna Nichols, Walsh Online- Chapter *Inflectional Synthesis of the Verb*. <https://wals.info/chapter/22>

synthetic forms of the verb in Albanian are constructed by means of inflections showing the person and the phonetic changes that the stem undergoes, simultaneously through inflections and phonetic changes, suffixes which are sometimes complemented with inflections showing the person and through suppletion complemented with inflections showing the person or suffixes.

In Albanian, the relation between the action and the subject of the sentence is expressed morphologically with two forms, in contrast with one another, the active and the passive forms of the verb.⁵⁸ The verbs in active voice in the first person singular of the present tense indicative mood have the ending *-j*, whereas verbs of the second conjugation where the final sound of the stem is a consonant and the verbs of the third conjugation with a vowel as the final sound of the stem do not have any inflections.

In the passive voice first person of the present tense indicative mood, the verbs' inflectional endings are *-em/-hem*.

According to the grammar of Albanian language⁵⁹ on the basis of the different relations between the action denoted by the verb and the subject of the sentence, as well as the opposition of the relevant forms (active-passive), there are four voices in Albanian: active, passive, reflexive and medium voice.

Verbs that belong to the *reflexive voice category* have their passive forms and denote an action that the subject performs and receives as well. In relation to the reflexive voice category, there is a sub-classification where the subject of the sentence represents the person acting on itself, and the verb is inherently reflexive, e.g. *krihem* 'comb myself', *lahem* 'wash myself', *vishem* 'dress myself'. When the subject stands for two or more person mutually acting on each other, then the verb is in the mutual reflexive voice, e.g. *përqafohem* 'hug', *përshëndetem* 'greet', *fejohem* 'get engaged'. These verbs are included in the medium voice category and are called mutual medium voice verbs.

Verbs belonging to the *medium voice* are in passive form and denote an action performed by the subject. The medium voice category comprises a group of verbs which denote movement such as *hidhem* 'jump', *kthehem* 'turn', *përpiqem* 'try', *rrotullohem* 'turn over'.

Some verbs denoting psychological-physiological actions such as *gëzohem* 'rejoice', *hidhërohe* 'grieve', *mërzitem* 'get bored', *kollem* 'cough') and some verbs that denote changes in physical, physiological, psychological state of the subject, such as *plakem* 'get old', *rrihem* 'grow', *tkurrem* 'shrink'. "In Albanian, the grammatical category of mood is the main means to express modality, which is the property of the non-finite forms of the verbs. Through the grammatical category of mood the speaker expresses his/her attitude towards the action denoted by the verb, presenting it as true, possible, desirable etc.⁶⁰ "In order to express these modality senses, Albanian in its historical development has created special grammatical indicators, which in some cases along with the meaning of the modality they express the meaning of tense."⁶¹

⁵⁸ Akademia e Shkencave të Shqipërisë, 1995.

⁵⁹ Akademia e Shkencave të Shqipërisë, 1995:270

⁶⁰ Akademia e Shkencave të Shqipërisë, 1995

⁶¹ Shaban Demiraj, *Gramatike e Gjuhës Shqipe*, 1986, f. 699-701. (Sami Frashëri & Kristofor Kristoforidhi, *Grammars Treat the Forms of the Admirative Mood as Forms of the Indicative and Subjunctive; with regard to the conditional mood.* Journal of Educational and Social Research MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy, Vol. 4 No.6 September 2014. <http://www.mcser.org/journal/index.php/jesr/article/viewFile/4068/3980/>

“In Albanian, the verb is used in six moods: the indicative, admirative, subjunctive, conditional, optative and imperative. Some grammars argue about the so-called subjunctive-admirative mood as a separate mood.

Some accept these verb forms as separate moods while others treat them as forms of the indicative mood. The admirative of the Albanian, in terms of its structure, is specific for Albanian and cannot be found in any of the Indo-European languages.⁶² The forms of the admirative are constructed by the abbreviated past participle form and the auxiliary *kam* (have). This argument was given for the first time by Dosdon and has been supported by the majority of linguists, it was not accepted by Jokli who thought that the admirative is constructed from the compounding of the inverted future form, this argument is not well supported as Demiraj also states.⁶³

The conditional mood expresses the modality of possibility. The verb in the conditional mood denotes an action that can be performed if the condition is met. The condition is often expressed by a subordinate conditional clause, whose verb is in past progressive tense or in the past perfect of the subjunctive mood. There are cases when it can be expressed by the adverb *ndryshe* (different), which would be used with the value of a cleft sentence or by a phrase consisting of the preposition *me* (with) or *pa* (without) and a noun.⁶⁴

In Albanian, verbs in optative mood have specific forms through them the speaker expresses a wish in the form of a wish or a curse. According to Demiraj,⁶⁵ the Albanian optative mood is relatively old, which is demonstrated by its uses in all its known functions in all dialects of Albanian, including here the dialect spoken by the Arberesh of Greece and Italy. There are different viewpoints with regard to how the forms of the verb in optative are structures.

According to Meyer and Pekmes, the origin of the optative is related to the present perfect of the Latin subjunctive mood, whereas Bopp and Pedersen argue that its origin is related to “aorist” of the subjunctive, this latter opinion is also supported by Domi and Demiraj. The documented verbal system of Albanian is quite rich intense forms, which express not only meaning differences of a tense character, but in some cases of an aspect nature as well.⁶⁶ The grammatical category of tense denotes the relationship between the time when the action denoted by the verb is performed and a certain moment, which is considered as the basis for time relations. This moment in speech is referred to as the moment of the speech, whereas for the written language as the moment when we are writing or another imagined moment. Therefore the main tenses of the verb are three: the present, the past and future.⁶⁷ On the basis of these three fundamental tenses there is a tense sub-classification. Not all the moods of the verb have the same number of grammatical tenses. This is due to the reason that “the type of modality of one mood or another condition even the existence or the use of a greater or a smaller number of tense forms”⁶⁸ Thus, the Albanian *indicative mood*, with regard to modality it is less marked than the other moods, is richer in verb tense forms. The indicative has ten tense forms: *the present, the past progressive, past simple,*

⁶² Shaban Demiraj, *Gramatika Historike e Gjuhës Shqipe*, 1986, f. 906 / f. 888.

⁶³ Shaban Demiraj, *Rreth Zhdukjes së Paskajores në Gjuhën Shqipe*, 1971, f. 33 – 34.

⁶⁴ Ethem Likaj, *Disa Çështje të Kategorisë Gramatikore të Diatezës në Gjuhën Shqipe*, 1997, f. 149 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Franz_Bopp

⁶⁵ Shaban Demiraj, *Gramatike e Gjuhes Shqipe I*, 1986, f. 708/ f. 709

⁶⁶ Shaban Demiraj, *Gramatike e Gjuhes Shqipe I*, 1986, f. 708/ f. 709

⁶⁷ Shaban Demiraj, *Gramatike e Gjuhes Shqipe I*, 1986, f. 708/ f. 709

⁶⁸ Shaban Demiraj, *Gramatike e Gjuhes Shqipe I*, 1986, f. 708 / f. 709

present perfect, past perfect, past perfect progressive, future simple, future perfect, future simple in the past, future perfect in the past. The admirative mood has four tense forms: *the present, the past progressive, present perfect and past perfect*. The conditional mood similar to the optative mood has only two tense forms, the present simple and the present perfect; in relation to the imperative there is not any tense opposition and in its forms do not express the grammatical category of tense⁶⁹ English verb system is largely periphrastic. Periphrasis, in contrast to inflection, is "a phrase of two or more words used to express a grammatical relationship that could otherwise be expressed by the inflection of a single word." All English verb forms except for the simple present and simple past are periphrastic. Although some grammars identify anywhere between twelve and sixteen English tenses, the nineteen finite, or conjugated, verb forms in English express more than just tense. To be more precise, English has:

Two tenses: *present and past*

Four aspects: *simple, progressive, perfect, perfect-progressive*

Three moods forms such as *indicative, subjunctive, imperative*.

Two voices: *active and passive*⁷⁰

Active voice (diateza veprore) tregon nje veprim qe e kryen vete kryefjala (ne kete rast kryefjala eshte vete vepruesi), kurse *passive voice* (diateza pesore) tregon nje veprim qe e peson kryefjala ku vepruesi mund te jete i shprehur gjuhesisht ose jo.⁷¹

4. 'Get' pasive

In English, the *be* auxiliary of a passive sentence may be substituted by *getting* to form "get-passives". Labov's experiments⁷² (1975, as cited in Weiner & Labov, 1983) showed that people generally interpret basic *get-* and *be-* passive sentences as semantically equivalent.

(a) The soldier *was* shot.

(b) The soldier *got* shot.

The passive voice places emphasis on the patient. In "get-passives", agents are usually omitted. Researchers have put forth various views on the semantic and pragmatic differences between *be-* and "get-passives". "Get-passives" are used when the events are "felt as having either fortunate or unfortunate consequences for the subject."⁷³ For instance, Chappell (1980)⁷⁴ offered an in-depth analysis of the *get-* passive by p. considering two categories of "get-passives", namely the non-reflexive "get-passives" (e.g. *Jane got fired*) and reflexive *get-*

⁶⁹ Akademia e Shkencave të Shqipërisë, 1995, f.327

⁷⁰ *English Verbs: Tense, Aspect, Mood, and Voice* <https://www.brightubeducation.com/english.../39260-the-english-verb-system-for-esl-st...>

⁷¹ Active and Passive Voice - Diateza Veprore dhe Pesore (5) <https://dokumen.tips/documents/active-and-passive-voice-diateza-veprore-dhe-pesore-5.html>

⁷² Agalliu, et al., Gramatika e Gjuhës Shqipe 1, *Morfologjia*, 2002, f. 330-341)

⁷³ Sami Ibrahim and Arburim Iseni, *Modern English Grammar*, 2008, f. 372, Infinitive or gerund.

⁷⁴ The Acquisition of English Passive Constructions, 2010, by Mandarin Speakers: a developmental perspective <https://researchdirect.westernsydney.edu.au/islandora/object/uws%3A8907>

passives (e.g. *Jane got herself fired*). Chappell's (*Is the Get-passive Adversative?* Sometimes can use 'get' in passive:

III. Methodology

3.1 Research methods

For this specific thesis the following methods have to be used: *Comparative method*, the focus will be on comparing the main phenomena analyzed in this research, namely *the morph syntax observation* of verbs in passives in Albanian and English. This research will be concentrated on what could be measured. It involves collecting and analyzing objective data that can be organized into statistics. The survey and experiment, it is going to be about the phenomena of English errors passive sentences made by 9th grade students of urban and rural secondary schools.

3.2 Research questions

The method of the study that is used here is quantitative research. Quantitative research applies for numbers from collecting the data, describing the data, until the result of research. The results of the test were described as they were in term of the existing condition without any interference of the researcher. The researcher collected the data through observations. It looked for the hypothesis that can explain the data collected or the facts which were observed. In this case, the researcher analyzed the sources of errors done by the students and type of errors made on both of 9th grade students in urban and rural Albanian secondary schools in using passive voice sentences. So, in this case, is described with giving any calculating procedure.

In this part, the major parts regarding passive voice in English and Albanian were clarified, dealing with the verb's category of voice, exactly speaking, concretely with passive voice and on its manifestation in both languages. The final part of this study was conducted through the comparative method in which the two passives were compared in order to find the differences and similarities that exist between them.

A few questions were set in this study with the main intention of finding the major information related to voice, in particular to the passive voice of the two represented languages. Through these questionnaire required proper answers for the passive's structure and utilization in both of the languages.

The study is based on the following questions:

What is the voice?

How is passive formed and what are its types?

Which are the cases that passive voice is chosen over active voice?

What are the similarities between English and Albanian passive voice?

What are the differences between English and Albanian passive voice?

3.3 *The participants*

To research on this topic, a total of 24 young Albanian learners of 9-th grade in an urban and rural secondary schools on the region of Dibra, Albania, the one in a rural region “Ploshtan Radomira” and the other in urban region “Selim Alliu” formed two groups for examining their errors make in passives will be interviewed, through a questionnaire. Participants of this study have to agree or disagree with the given statements. Statements are related to learning practices, advantages of learning a second language in early age, problems learners face while learning English, practices used, integration of them in L2, etc.

3.4 *Data analysis*

Corder (1967 & 1974) identifies a model for error analysis which includes the following three stages:

1. Data collection
2. Description
3. Explanation which is considered to be the ultimate object of error analysis

However, Brown (1994: 207-211) and Ellis (1995: 51-52) elaborate on this model. Ellis (1997:15-20) and Hubbard et al. (1996:135-141) gave practical advice and provided clear examples of how to identify and analyze learners’ errors.

The technique of Collecting Data Sugiyono (2013:148) state that instrument is a device that used to measure the natural and social phenomena are observed. The data was in the form of numbers taken from the tests that were conducted before and after the cycles done. In collecting data, the researcher used two types of techniques: 1. Observation: The observation included viewing the techniques of teaching passive voice in the classroom. 2. Test: Testing is an important part of the teaching and learning process. Sanjaya (2013:251) state that test is the instruments to collect data on the ability of the subject of research by measuring. Brown (2004:3) defines a test as a method of measuring a person’s ability, knowledge, or performance in a given domain. The test also defines as the series of questions which is used to measure the skill, knowledge, or performance in a given area. The test is a series of questions or other instruments, which are used to measure the individual or group skill, knowledge, intelligence, capability or talent. According to Dullay’s (1982) theory and Azar’s (1992), misformation could be classified into several groups: a. Past Participle. b. Be c. Addition. d. Word Omission. e. Subject – Object. f. By phrase. g. Singular – Plural.

The aim of this research was to discuss errors made by the 9-th grade in rural and urban secondary school students, in using passive voice in written English, and find out whether these errors can be attributed to the learners' lack of knowledge, misformation of grammar rules and interference of the mother tongue or other causes. The data of this research were the results of the test given by the teacher containing active voice sentences that must be changed by the students into passive voices. The student’s answers were used by the teacher to be analyzed. To provide

data for the error analysis, the researcher needs to collect a sample of learner language. In this step, the researcher may control the data by specifying the sample he/she intends to collect. The source of the data was the students' test which was given by the teacher to the 24 students of the 9-th grade of rural and urban secondary schools students.

3.5 The purpose of this study

The purpose of this study is to show and clarify the form, usage, and division of passive voice in both English and Albanian language, and further examine some properties of the passive through a close comparison of two languages in between the two. Furthermore, it intends to find out the linguistic and extra-linguistic reasons for choosing passive constructions in different contexts.

3.6 Error/Data collection

A sample of written work was collected from 24 students of the 9th grade of two urban and rural schools.

No.	Category	Number of students' errors in the 9-th grade in an urban school	Number of students' errors in the 9-th grade in a rural school	Percentage % of wrong & right answers of the 9th grade in an urban school	Percentage % of wrong & right answers of the 9-th grade in a rural school
1	Incorrect use of present participle & past participle	20	28	33.4%	46.7%
		14 (omission1)	16	41.6%	44.5%
	Correct use of present participle & past participle	40	32	66.6%	53.3%
2	Incorrect tense used (past participle)	48	73	20 %	30.4%
		175	141	72.9%	58.8 %
	Unwritten tense	17	26	7.1%	10.8%
3	Incorrect use of the verb 'to be'	64	58	26.7%	24.2%
		149 (112)	101	62%	42%
	The omission of 'be'	27	81	11.3%	33.8%
4	Inorrect passive sentences	149	197	62%	82%
		74	17	31%	7%
	Correct passive sentences	17	26	7%	11%
5	Misordering passives	16	38	26.6%	64%
		35	17	58.4%	28.3%
	Unwritten pasive sentences	9	5	15%	8.3%

	Unwritten pasive sentences				
6	Incorrect use form of "have"	17	14	15.8%	12.5%
	The omission of "have"	2	1		
7	Incorrect use of 'by' – phrase	19	22	79%	92%
	The omission of "by"	35	74	15%	30%
8	Incorrect translation	39	66	32%	55%
	Correct translation	67	43	56.3%	36%
	Unwritten sentences	14	11	11.7%	9%
9	Incorrect use of 'be' & 'get'	44	46	61%	64%
		32	39	67%	81%
		28	26	39%	36%
	Correct use of 'be' & 'get'	16	9	33%	19%
10	Incorrect use of Participle & Adjective	44	56	37%	47 %
		41	50	34%	42%
		76	64	63%	53%
	Correct use of Participle & Adjective	79	70	66%	58%
11	Misformation of subject-object pronouns change	19	36	79%	15%
12	Misformation of modals	7 (omission 1)	5	29%	21%

The above table shows the results of the students' performance with reference to the use of the correct sentences. The correct answers were calculated as well as the incorrect answers. The results were also arranged in a table containing the percentage for each item.

3.7 Students' test

The teacher observed the students' tests in using passive voice and common errors made in each tense. The teacher used the tests consisted in some tenses, such as the simple present, present continuous, present perfect, simple past, past continuous, past perfect, simple future (including the form of "be going to"). The teacher took the students' answers from the test. In the process of collecting data, the teacher collected the students' answers from the test to be read attentively and underlined the errors in order to find and identify the erroneous sentences to be analyzed.

In this study, students were handed an achievement test that includes seven sets of the teacher's questionnaire. The time devoted to answering this test was 60 minutes.

The first set of questions includes (10) items. They are the tenses of verbs. Students were asked to change the sentences in passive.

The second set of questions includes (10) items. In this set, students were asked to translate English passives in Albanian. This test is to examine students' ability how correctly they translate sentences in their mother's language

The third set of questions includes (10) items, consisting the use of "be" versus "get". In this set, students are asked to use correctly the verb "be" and "get" passive.

The fourth set of questions includes (10) items, the students must use correctly "participles" or "adjectives". This set is to test their ability to use properly past *participles* with *adjectives* ending both in "-ed".

The fifth set of questions includes (5) items, the students have to put correctly in order the passive sentences. This test is to examine how correctly they write them ordering.

The sixth set of questions includes (10) items, includes the passive change of sentences, too. The students must use correctly the passive sentences as an example given. This test is to examine the correctness of changing the passives. It is a mixed set of questions, where the students must use correctly the sentence order, the correctness use of "by" versus "from", correctness use of the verb "be", changing correctly pronouns as *subject* and *object* passives, the correct use of all tenses, the correctness of modals.

The last and the seventh set of questions includes (8) items, students are asked to write correctly the mix of *present* and *past participle*, adjectives ending in "-ing" and "ed". This test is to examine students' performance in forming active and passive sentences.

3.8 Students' questionnaire

A questionnaire has been used in this study to serve as a research tool in eliciting supplementary source data. Twelve copies of each questionnaire on both 9-th grade rural and urban secondary schools were distributed in self-addressed envelopes many of which were completed on the spot. Teachertest's questionnaire contained sixty-three sentences in all. All these questions focus on the major points related to passive voice. The choice of questions was based on or related to the teacher's experience in the teaching field, as well as the teacher's familiarities with the curriculum of 9-th grade students of rural and urban secondary schools. The main objectives of the students' questionnaire were to show the students' point of view regarding the ability of them in learning and understanding passive voice.

4. Identifications of errors

Interference from the mother tongue is clearly a major source of difficulty in second language learning. Many errors, however, derive from the strategies employed by the learner in language acquisition, and from the mutual interference of items within the target language. There are other sources of errors as identified by Richard (1974:174-76) these include: (1). Intralingual transfer (over-generalization) (2). Ignorance of rule restrictions (3). Incomplete application of rules. (4). False conceptshypothesized.

The identification of errors involves a comparison between learners' sentences and native speakers' sentences in the same context. The teacher analyzed each student's errors in student's test. There are problems with the formations of passive (misformation of passive verb; active

order but passive form; absent or wrong prepositions, omission of 'by-phrase' or incorrect use of it, incorrect use of present versus past participle, misformation of tense used, irregular of 'be' and 'have', incorrect use of object pronouns, incorrect use in translation, etc. There were ten types that were allocated in this research, which about the types of errors commonly made by the students in using passive voice and a common error made by the student in each tense. The research focused with sentences in some tenses, such as simple present, present continuous, present perfect, simple past, past continuous, past perfect, simple future (including 'be going to' form). In observation, the teacher gave advice to the students to only focus on the selected given test, because of that according to the student's ability.

4.1 The results of the students' test

The following shows the results of all sets of questions (the multiple choice). These results were arranged in one table containing the right responses as well as the wrong responses, and the percentage of the right answers and the wrong answers were calculated for each item. The results of the teachers' questionnaire taken from students of the 9-th grade in urban and rural schools, will be shown as below: *In the first and sixth set of questions* were concerned with whether the students find difficulties to change active voice sentences to passive. Also the difficulty in changing correctly the *subject* and *object pronouns* during the passive, the correctness of the use of 'by phrase' versus 'from' or other prepositions, the correctness of using *past participle* of main verbs, correctness of using verb 'be', correctness of verb 'have', also the correct use of modals. From 240 sentences in all students of 9-th grade urban school test, were found 149 incorrect use of passive sentences or 62%, 74 incorrect use of sentences or 31%, unwritten passive sentences 17 or 7%. From 240 sentences in all students of the 9-th grade rural school test, were found: 197 incorrect use of passive sentences or 82%, 17 incorrect use of sentences or 7%, unwritten passive sentences 26 or 11%. Other results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade urban school test in past *participle tense* used, were found: 48 incorrect tenses used (past participle) or 20 %, 175 correct tense used (past participle) or 72.9 %, 17 unwritten or 7.1 %. Other results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade rural school test in past *participle tense* used, were found: 73 incorrect tenses used (past participle) or 30.4 %, 141 correct tenses used (past participle) or 58.8 %, 26 unwritten or 10.8 %. Results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade urban school test in using verb 'have', were found: 17 + 2 omission incorrect tense used (past participle) or 15.8 %. Results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade rural school test in using verb 'have', were found: 14 + 1 omission incorrect tense used (past participle) or 12.5 %. Results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade urban school test in using 'by' – phrase, were found: 19 incorrect use of 'by' – phrase or 79 %. 35 omission of 'by' or 15 %. Results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade rural school test in using 'by' – phrase, were found: 22 incorrect use of 'by' – phrase or 92 %. 74 omission of 'by' or 30%.

Results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade urban school test in changing *subject and object pronouns*, were found: 19 incorrect use *subject and object pronouns* or 79 %. Results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade rural school test in changing *subject and object pronouns*, were found: 36

misformations *subject and object pronouns* or 15 %. Results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade urban school test in the use of *modals*, were found: 8 misformation of *modals* or 29 %. Results of 240 sentences of 9-th grade rural school test in the use of *modals*, were found: 5 misformation use *subject and object pronouns* or 21 %. *In the second set of questions* was concerned with whether the students find difficulties in the translation of sentences in mother's tongue. The results of 120 sentences of 9-th grade urban school test, were found: 39 incorrect translate sentences or 32 %, 67 incorrect translate sentences or 56.3%, unwritten sentences 14 or 11.7%. The results of 120 sentences of 9-th grade rural school test, were found: 66 incorrect translate sentences or 55 %, 67 incorrect translate sentences or 56.3 %, unwritten sentences 11 or 9 %. *In the third set of questions* was concerned with whether the students find difficulties in using correctly the verb "be" versus "get". The results of 120 sentences of 9-th grade urban school test 72 of them belong to the verb "be" and 48 belong to the verb "get", were found: 44 incorrect use of "be" or 61%, 32 incorrect use of "get" or 67%, 28 correct use of "be" or 39%, 16 correct use of "get" or 33 %. The results of 120 sentences of 9-th grade rural school test 72 of them belong to the verb "be" and 48 belong to the verb "get", were found: 46 incorrect use of "be" or 64 %, 39 incorrect use of "get" or 81 %, 26 correct use of "be" or 36 %, 9 correct use of "get" or 19 %. *In the fourth set of questions* was concerned with whether the students find difficulties in using correctly the *participles* versus *adjectives* ending in *-ing* form. The results of 120 sentences of 9-th grade urban school test, were found: 44 incorrect use of "participle" or 37%, 41 incorrect use of "adjective" or 34 %, 76 correct use of "participle" or 63 %, 79 correct use of "adjective" or 66%. The results of 120 sentences of 9-th grade rural school test were found: 56 incorrect use of "participle" or 47 %, 50 incorrect use of "adjective" or 42 %, 64 correct use "participle" or 53 %, 70 correct use of "adjective" or 58 %. *In the fifth set of questions* was concerned with whether the students find difficulties in writing correctly passive sentence order. The results of 60 sentences in all of the 9-th grade urban school test of "misordering passive", were found: 149 incorrect use of "misordering passive" or 62%, 74 correct use of "misordering passive" or 31%, 17 unwritten *passive sentences* or 7%. The results of 60 sentences in all of the 9-th grade rural school test of "misordering passive", were found: 197 incorrect use of "misordering passive" or 82%, 17 correct use of "misordering passive" or 7 %, 26 unwritten *passive sentences* or 11 %. *In the seventh set of questions* was concerned with whether the students find difficulties in choosing correctly *present participle* or *past participle* of adjectives. The results of 96 sentences in all of "present participle" of *adjective* sentences ending in *-ing* and "past participle" of *adjective* sentences ending in *-ed* form of 9-th grade urban school test, were found: 20 incorrect use of "present participle" or 33.4% ,15 incorrect use of "past participle" or 41.6 %. 40 correct "present participle" or 66.6 %, 21 correct use of "past participle" or 58.3 %. The results of 96 sentences in all of "present participle" ending in *-ing* and "past participle" sentences ending in *-ed* form of 9-th grade rural school test, were found: 28 incorrect use of "present participle" or 46.7% , 16 incorrect use of "past participle" or 44.5 % , 32 correct "present participle" or 53.3 % , 20 correct use of "past participle" or 55.5 %. The rest of the errors have happened using incorrectly the addition of other words as:

The addition of verb ‘‘be’’ in urban school test were 3 and in rural school test was 1. Also, the addition of verb ‘‘have’’ in urban school test were 4 and in rural school test were 2. An addition is to a noun in an urban school test. An addition is to the verb ‘‘do’’. As it looked the addition errors were not so wrongly considerable in contrastive to the other passive errors shown on the table above. From the analysis of the teachers' questionnaire, the results confirmed that most of the 9-th grade secondary school students at rural and urban schools in the region of Dibra, Albania, committed errors and faced difficulties in learning and understanding the meaning of passive voice in written English. Those difficulties were systematic errors such as interference of the mother tongue, over-generalization, ignorance of rule restriction, incomplete application of rules and false concept hypothesized.

Most students' answers of 9th grade urban and rural secondary schools faced great difficulties to change sentences from active to passive. The majority of students did not know the rule of forming verb ‘‘to be’’ in all tenses. They lacked the knowledge about the grammar of the English language as well in their mother's tongue, too. Students had difficulties in learning and memorizing the past participle of verbs. Also, they had difficulties using *by*-phrase whom they often omitted it, or wrong used of verb ‘‘have’’, and modals, too. They even had difficulties in writing correctly the order of passive sentences. Changing correctly the subject and object pronouns were other difficulties faced by students. Other errors were the adding of some unnecessary words during the use of passive sentences.

Differences of 9-th grade urban versus rural secondary schools students

Other observations of teacher's test were the contrastive analysis of both 9-th grade students in urban and rural secondary schools of Dibra region. As it was shown from the teacher's test it's a big difference error made from students of 9-th grade rural students compared to those 9-th grade students. Incorrectness of *participles* were 33.4% to 46.7%, incorrectness of *tense* used were 20% to 30.4%, incorrectness of verb ‘‘be’’ were 26.7% to 24.2%, incorrectness of passive sentences were 62% to 80%, unwritten passive sentences were 7% to 11%, misordering of passive were 26.6% to 64%, incorrectness use of have were 15.8% to 12.5%, incorrectness use of ‘‘by’’ were 79% to 92% and omission 15% to 30%, incorrectness translation were 56.3% to 36%, incorrectness of ‘‘be’’ versus ‘‘get’’ were 61% to 64% and 67% to 81%, incorrectness of *participles* versus *adjectives* ending in -ed were 37% to 47% and 34% to 42%, misformation use of *subject-object* passive change was 79% to 15% and finally misformation use of *modals* were 29% to 21%. As the above results on both 9-th grade urban and rural secondary schools the percentages were in a big gap of incorrectnesses of the majority of test's issues during using the passives. In urban schools, the quality of errors is lower than those to rural schools. Otherwise in rural schools is higher. This, as my point of view, happens because in urban schools the quality of students is better than in rural schools. Why?

In urban schools the quality of teaching methods is higher, because they are more motivated for many reasons. The school infrastructure is better in some directions. The funds are invested more in school infrastructure, also in any other directions. The students are more

educated in urban schools as a result of being frequently more caring from their families than rural school students families, raising the quality of their learning. The frequency of students in urban schools in being part of English courses is permanent as inside the schools as outside. The number of schools in urban schools is very comparable to rural schools, in making students multi choices. The reason for students in improving their English in urban schools is dominant to rural students, being aware of their future, so the investing of their families to their children is more appropriate. The immigrations in rural areas has lowered the quality in learning, as their family caring is less demand.

IV. Results

Findings based on the contrastive analysis between English and Albanian passive

Although English and Albanian belong to the Indo-European family, still many similarities and differences had been found out. Based on the descriptive analysis of the examples that had been presented in the previous sections regarding passive voice, its formation, usage, resemblance and variation between the respective languages it turns out that: *The similarities were:*

In both languages, a special morphological marking appeared on the verb. Same rules were applied for changing a verb from active to passive. The active clause that had an object was converted into the passive and the direct object of that active clause become the subject of the passive clause. The helping verb 'to be' and the main verb of the active voice change into *the past participle* form when turned into the passive.

1. Both languages needed a transitive verb in an active sentence to be able to change into a passive form. English had a simpler verbal system.

2. In both English and Albanian passive sentences, the object in the active sentence becomes the subject in the passive sentence and the subject becomes the part of "by phrase" or "prej / nga",

3. In both English and Albanian passive voice the "by phrase" or "prej / nga" could be left if it is not essential to the meaning of the sentence.

4. In both languages, the omission of the verb "be" were the same, in a contextual meaning. *The differences were:*

1. The formula of the English passive voice was different from the Albanian passive voice. The English passive voice used verb "be" and the *pastparticiple* verbs consisting of regular (-ed prefixes) and irregular verbs, while the Albanian passive verbs it had not any particularly distinguished from that (vetvetores) the active and passive of subject than (trajtat pesore me mbaresat) -em, -esh, etj + pjesezen "u" (u lava) and the verb + participle e foljes kryesore. (punuar, lare, sjelle, ndenj~~ur~~). The English passive verbs dealt with tenses; on the other hand, in Albanian, there were no tenses because the time reference does not determine the verb forms in the sentence to express the time signal.

The linguistic error was made by the students in the category misformation of passive infinitive of English has the characteristics of aspect (perfective, *to have worked*), passive form (*to be taught*) dhe te polarity (possessive: *to go*, negative: *not to go*). Albanian had not the

characteristics of the *verb aspect*, so the *infinitive* could not have this aspect. The passive voice was more frequently used in the English language than in the Albanian language. While the English voice was divided into active and passive only, Albanian language was divided into *active, passive, middle and reflexive voice as well*.

Misformation of future tense ‘*going to*’, which was not common in Albanian. Error category of *conditional passive* misformation in Albanian was formed from ‘*do te*’ + the verb in the past progressive passive. *Past simple passive conditional* was formed from ‘*do te*’ + jam in past progressive + particle (do te isha zene ose e ardhmja e perparme e se shkuare). Gjuha shqipe eshte e ndryshme dhe ne ‘‘Habitore’’ e ‘‘Deshirore’’ qe ne anglisht nuk egziston. Zgjedhimi vepror ne shqip ne mohore dhe percjellore: *pa qene lare, pa qene hapur, duke qene lare, duke qene hapur*. Ndersa dialektale dhe ne paskajore e llojit ‘*me la*’ haset vetem ne te folmet Gege ‘*me qene la*’, ‘*me qene hapur*’. Whereas the error of *misformation of modal verbs* in the passive voice, *misformation of present continuous in passive*. In English made by verb ‘‘be’’ (am, is, are) + be+ing + ing of the main verb, whereas in Albanian ‘‘jam’ + pjesezen’’u’’+ pjesore e foljes qe mban veprimin. (Albanian knows only present participle).

As far as the passive word order in English was concerned, it follows the generally fixed word formation, with the agent always appearing after the passive verb form. In the otherhand, the Albanian language was described as a free word order language, with the agent appearing before and after the passive verb.

Based on the *Comparative Linguistic Taxonomy*, the source of the students’ error was found. All of their errors happened because of the interference of their first language which is called an interlingual error. Moreover, they are more familiar with the active voice better than passive voice, and they like to use passive voice in their writing. Therefore, they made such errors in changing active voice into passive voice.

V. Conclusions

This diploma paper provided clear definitions of voice category for English and Albanian language. In both languages, voice shared the same meaning and function. Thus, the voice is a grammatical category that makes it possible to view the action of a sentence in two different ways without changes in the facts reported. In consequence, passive voice in the English language was divided into different types as follow: *short and long passive; di-transitive passive; be-passive, get-passive and bare passive; verbal passive and adjectival passive; prepositional passive*. In Albanian language passive voice distinguishes only based on its tool of the formation. The tools through which passive voice in Albanian was formed were: endings, the helping verb *jam*, and the clitic *-u*. However, there were a few cases in which passive voice is preferred over active voice. The situations in which passive is used over active are: when the receiver of the action is more important than the doer, when the doer is unknown or too well-known to require mention, and in scientific writings, as it helps establish a tone of detachment and impersonality.

Recommendations

Because in the teaching and learning process, there are many things to be considered. On the basis of this study, the following recommendations should be taken into consideration:

1. Teachers of English should provide students with a list of sentences of both forms (active and passive), and ask students to classify these sentences to active and passive.
2. They should also teach their students all forms of the verb to be i.e. (all tenses).
3. Teachers should provide a list of verbs in present, past and past participle forms and ask students to memorize them.
4. Teachers should help students notice the difference between parts of the sentence.
5. Students should be exposed to many exercises to overcome their difficulties.
6. They should be addressed to learn how to change active to passive and vice versa.
7. Teachers should teach how to use correctly "by" phrase.
8. They should be teaching their students how to change correctly the subject-object pronouns.
9. They should teach to translate correctly in their mother's tongue.
10. The students should be motivated by using passive.

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